

Heterocyclic Steroids. Part II*: An Unusual Product in the Cyclodehydration of γ -(7-Methoxy-2-Methyl-2H-Chromene-4) Butyric Acid**

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Attempted cyclodehydration of the bicyclic acid (2a, R = H) under the catalysis of anhydrous ferric chloride in acetic anhydride afforded a most unusual product, 3-acetyl-7-methoxy-2-methylchromone instead of the expected tricyclic unsaturated ketone.

THE synthesis of γ -(7-methoxy-2-methyl-2H-chromene-4)-butyric acid (2a; R = H) as a key-intermediate for the total synthesis of 6-oxa-7-methylestrone methyl ether (4)† (Scheme A) was earlier achieved in these laboratories in three steps starting with 7-methoxy-2-methylchroman-4-one (1) (Scheme A). The next step in the synthetic scheme involves the cyclodehydration of the bicyclic dihydroacid (2a; R = H) to furnish the expected tricyclic conjugated ketone (3) (Scheme A). Attempted cyclization of (2a) under a variety of conditions‡ was, however, found to be of little success in affording the desired unsaturated ketone (3).

Scheme A

When anhydrous ferric chloride in acetic anhydride was employed for cyclodehydration of 2a, a dark semi-solid mass was isolated as a neutral product. Purification by chromatography followed by short-path distillation of this product afforded a light yellow solid (17%) which on recrystallization from hexane afforded (5) as almost colorless crystals, m.p. 156-158°C.

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‡ Lewis acids such as anhydrous zinc chloride, PPA or PTS, P₂O₅ and SnCl₄ (employing the acid chloride of the bicyclic acid Ca) were all employed in this cyclodehydration reaction but with no success.

Elemental composition and the appearance of the molecular ion peak at m/e 232 (100%) in its mass spectrum ruled out the anticipated structure (3) for this FeCl₃-catalysed reaction product (5). The u.v. (ethanol) of (5) indicated absorption maxima at 247 (ϵ 10,950), 274 (ϵ 4,389) and at 304 nm (ϵ 2,640) which are very characteristic of 7-methoxychromone system¹. The i.r. (CH₂Cl₂) spectrum of (5) indicated bands at 1690 (arylconjugated C = O), 1640 (β -diketone) and 1625 cm⁻¹ (olefinic C = C) which supported not only the assigned structure for this product (5) but were also in agreement with the i.r. data reported for such 3-acetylchromones by Molho and Brun².

Further, confirmation of the structure (5) for this FeCl₃-catalysed reaction product was achieved by a detailed study of its n.m.r. and mass spectral characteristics.

The typical absence of signals due to methylene protons in the n.m.r. spectrum of (5) indicated clearly the loss of butyric acid side-chain in the starting acid (2a; R = H) during this reaction. The appearance of the C₅-proton signal as a doublet centred at τ 1.9 ($J_{H,H} = 8.5$ Hz) in the n.m.r. spectrum is quite interesting. The same C₅-proton in the bicyclic ester (2b; R = CH₃) corresponding to the acid (2a; R = H) appeared at τ 2.2 ($J_{H,H} = 8.5$ Hz). The observed paramagnetic shift (ca 0.3 ppm) of the signal for this peri-proton at C₅ in the n.m.r. spectrum of (5) was ascribed to a deshielding effect of the carbonyl function at C₄ in the product (5). Badawi and Fayez³ who made extensive n.m.r. studies on natural and synthetic chromones also noticed such a down-field shift for this C₅-proton signal in chromones due to the deshielding effect of the carbonyl function of the γ -pyrone system.

The aforesaid shift of the C₅-proton signal in the n.m.r. spectrum of (5) clearly indicated the presence of a carbonyl function at C₄ in this FeCl₃-catalysed reaction product (5). The signals due to the other aromatic protons at C₈ and C₆ appeared as expected⁴ at τ 3.2 (d, $J_{H,H} = 2.5$ Hz) and τ 3.1 (a pair of doub-

lets, $J_{H,H} = 8.5$ Hz; $J_{H,H} = 2.5$ Hz). The typical absence of a signal at τ 5.55 in the spectrum due to the C_2 -methine proton together with the observed large paramagnetic shift of the C_2 -methyl signal (τ 7.55) in the n.m.r. spectrum of (5) as compared to the same signal in the n.m.r. spectrum of its bicyclic ester (2a; R = CH_3) pointed out clearly a chromone skeleton for this unusual product (5). In fact in a majority of natural chromones, the C_2 -methyl appears at τ 7.64 in the n.m.r. spectrum as reported by Badawi and Fayez³. The other singlet of 3H intensity at τ 7.38 was ascribed to the methyl group of the acetyl function at C_3 of this unusual product (5).

The mode of mass spectral fragmentation indicated in Scheme B for this product (5) was not only in good agreement with the assigned structure (5) but also consistent with the mode of fragmentation claimed for 3-acetyl-5,7-dihydroxy-2-methylchromone by Badawi and his associates⁵. This product (5) was finally identified as 3-acetyl-7-methoxy-2-methylchromone by mixed m.p. determination and i.r. comparison in chloroform solution with that of an authentic sample prepared in accordance with the procedure reported by Baker and Butt⁶.

Experimental

The two m.p.s reported herein are uncorrected. Ultraviolet spectrum was determined in 95% ethanol using M4PMQ II Carl zeiss spectrophotometer. Infrared spectrum was determined using Perkin-Elmer 421 spectrophotometer. NMR spectrum was

recorded on Varian A60A spectrometer using TMS as internal standard; the chemical shifts are reported in τ -values.

Attempted FeCl₃-catalysed cyclodehydration of the bicyclic dihydro acid (2a; R = H) (Scheme A): To a solution of 1.5 g of the bicyclic dihydroacid (2a; R = H), m.p. 210°C, in 20 ml of freshly distilled acetic anhydride was added 3.5 g of anhydrous ferric chloride. The resulting mixture was stirred vigorously at 55–60°C for 4 hr in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed with ice-water. The resulting dark green slurry was then extracted with ether (3 × 40 ml) and the ethereal layer washed with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (4 × 20 ml) and water (3 × 20 ml). Evaporation of the dried ether extract afforded a dark semi-solid mass (0.9 g; 25% yield). This material was chromatographed over activated neutral Brockmann alumina (E.M.) (30 g) (activated at 180°C/2 mm for 3 hr). The benzene fraction afforded a yellow sticky-solid in 17% yield, which on trituration with hexane solidified. Repeated recrystallization from *n*-hexane gave the analytical sample of 3-acetyl-7-methoxy-2-methylchromone (5) as almost colourless crystals, m.p. 156–158°C (reported², m.p. 160°C). These crystals on exposure for long time used to turn yellow. A similar behaviour was also noticed by Baker and Butt⁶ for the same chromone (5) (Found: C, 67.47; H, 5.37; calc. for C₁₃H₁₂O₄: C, 67.23; H, 5.17%).

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